

Topological interlocking assemblies based on origami inspired carbon-reinforced concrete waterbomb modules

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Abstract

The integration of origami-inspired design principles into architecture and engineering has led to significant advances in the development of innovative modular structural systems. Examples of such systems are slabs and walls, which can be designed through the assembly of thin-walled folded carbon-reinforced concrete (CRC) modules based on the waterbomb origami principle. The CRC waterbomb modules inherently possess geometric symmetry and compatibility properties. Therefore, tessellations consisting of these modules can be easily designed with high precision by means of algebraic methods.

In order to construct such tessellations from CRC modules, the waterbomb base cells have to be modified by introducing slits near the creases of the given cells. In this paper, the resulting waterbomb modules are described. The new tessellations that result from these waterbomb modules form suitable candidates for topological interlocking assemblies, i.e. arrangements of 3D-geometries which are kinematically constrained by fixed frames. This property is proven mathematically. Furthermore, the challenges of constructing the described assemblies with non-zero and zero thickness modules are discussed.

1 Introduction

In recent years, it has been recognized that carbon-reinforced concrete (CRC) provides numerous benefits over standard steel-reinforced concrete, as noted for example in [1-2]. In particular, construction with CRC offers advantages in terms of strength, reduced weight, and improved corrosion resistance, positioning CRC as a viable material for thin, efficient, and sustainable designs.

Nowadays, novel approaches for creating innovative modular structural systems consisting of CRC components draw inspiration from origami. For instance, the ability to transform a planar tessellation into different folded three-dimensional geometries opens up various possibilities to construct such modular systems. A well-known origami pattern which can be exploited for this purpose is the waterbomb tessellation, see [3]. It forms a periodic arrangement of a base cell made up of two mountain and four valley creases. Chuboda et al. [4] present an exact algebraic parametrization of this waterbomb base cell and the arising tessellation, where the parameters encode the edge lengths and folding angles of the base cell. In this paper, we present an individual waterbomb module that is derived from the waterbomb base cell and facilitates a topological interlocking assembly.

Here, an arrangement of rigid modules together with a fixed frame is called a *topological interlocking assembly (TIA)*, if the frame enforces every non-empty finite subset of modules of the arrangement to be kinematically constrained and thus these subsets cannot be removed from the arrangement. Note that the term *frame* does not refer to a fixed boundary around the assembly, but it is introduced for the purpose of proving the interlocking property, denoting a subset of modules within the entire assembly that are kinematically constrained at certain points.[^]

Note that the study of TIAs as a material design concept has been initiated by Estrin et al. see [5-6] for a few references. For more investigations dealing with the construction of TIAs, we refer the reader to [7-12].

We describe the construction of waterbomb modules that are derived from waterbomb base cells. These modules consist of overlapping segments of waterbomb base cells and are constructed by introducing slits parallel to the valley creases. The waterbomb modules are manufacturing using the casting fold-in-fresh methodology developed by [13] using the pneumatic folding tool introduced in [14]. In the fold-in-fresh methodology, the concrete are casted in layers and the carbon-reinforcement is added in between these layers. After the casting, the foldwork that replicates the kinematics of the waterbomb pattern is folded while the concrete is still in fresh state. We describe corresponding arrangements and prove that these arrangements form TIAs, based on the precise definition of a TIA given in [12].

This paper is structured as follows: First, a description of the proposed waterbomb modules with and without thickness is given, see Section 2. Then, in Section 3, the assembly process of these waterbomb modules is discussed with special emphasis on the challenges that arise from assembling real-life modules made of CRC with non-zero thickness and construction imperfections. Finally, a mathematical proof of the interlocking property for a family of assemblies of the zero thickness waterbomb modules with different frames is presented in Section 4.

2 Waterbomb module

A waterbomb module is constructed according to a waterbomb base cell and its corresponding design parameters a , b , c and e_x as illustrated in Fig. 1 a). For an algebraic description of the base cell and the resulting tessellations, we refer to [4]. Using the symmetry and compatibility characteristics of the waterbomb pattern, a tessellation of these waterbomb base cells can be constructed as shown in Fig. 1 b). Considering the feasibility of transforming this pattern into a construction element with structural functionality that facilitates modular assembly, we can merge a central base cell with one-quarter of its adjacent neighbors, as illustrated in the highlighted rectangle of Fig. 1 b). Furthermore, the flat pattern in xy -plane yields a folded state in \mathbb{R}^3 , controlled by the design parameter γ , as depicted in Fig. 1 c). To transform the zero thickness module into a CRC module, a thickness t is introduced as an additional design parameter. To enable the assembly of the thick CRC modules and exploit its symmetry, periodicity, and compatibility properties, slits are added as a geometrical feature, as seen in Fig. 1 d). The resulting module is called a *waterbomb module*. The slits facilitate the assembly of the modules via sliding. Then a TIA is realized by constructing a suitable frame constraining the entire assembly. The dimensions of these slits determine the contact area between the neighboring modules, which is directly related to the stress transfer between the modules throughout the structure. The waterbomb modules are casted adding layers of concrete and reinforcement on top of the formwork in flat-state, then the formwork is folded, while the concrete is still fresh. Then, the web is casted with the same concrete and reinforcement layers parallel to the y -axis, see Fig. 1 d).

Fig. 1: Design of the waterbomb modules: (a) Definition of the base cell based on the waterbomb origami pattern. (b) Tessellation formed by base cells. (c) Folded zero thickness waterbomb module. (d) CAD representation of the carbon reinforced-concrete module and its dimensions.

3 Assembly process

The assembly procedure of waterbomb modules is a critical step in the construction of a structural system that forms a TIA. Transforming our theoretical design concept into CRC elements that fulfill a structural purpose poses challenges for the assembly. In this section, we provide an explanation and suggestions for the further development of assemblies of CRC waterbomb modules.

3.1 Concept of a waterbomb assembly

The assembly process of the waterbomb modules leverages the symmetry and periodicity inherent in the tessellation. The modules are assembled by fully sliding modules together along their diagonal slits.

The waterbomb module has diagonal slits oriented in two non-parallel directions, requiring a strategic assembly approach to ensure that the positioning of one module does not obstruct the assembly of subsequent modules. The need for an assembly strategy is due to the geometric constraints that prevent the simultaneous insertion of two slits with non-parallel diagonal orientations. Based on that, the strategy required for a successful assembly is depicted in Fig. 2. The modules are initially built by connecting them through the slits in a diagonal direction, as indicated by the blue arrows in Fig. 2, resulting in diagonal arrangements of waterbomb modules. It is imperative to include the half-modules that close the assembly at the peripheries in this step of the assembly process; otherwise, their addition in later insertion steps will be infeasible. The diagonal arrangement of modules is now connected to the adjacent diagonal arrangement of modules, as illustrated by the red arrows in Fig. 2. Once all diagonal arrangements are assembled and the peripheral frame is in place, the final tessellation is completed and configures a TIA.

Fig. 2: Assembly process by a diagonal pattern

3.2 Challenges in assembling carbon reinforced-concrete modules

Theoretically, the waterbomb modules attain a flawless fit and uncomplicated assembly when the modules are stiff, free of imperfections and zero thickness due to the precise alignment of the crease lines and facet normals, ensuring a perfect TIA. Translating the principles of a waterbomb module and its assembly into tangible construction elements, such as carbon-reinforced concrete modules, poses challenges in the manufacturing process, tolerances, geometric considerations, assembly procedures, and structural performance.

The focus of this subsection lies on the challenges associated with the assembly process. During the assembly process, the self-weight of the CRC module initiates a rearrangement of the modules, where the assembled modules will move until they reach an equilibrium state. This movement occurs in varying magnitudes, as it is a phenomenon contingent upon the geometrical manufacturing imperfections and deformation of the modules.

Moreover, CRC modules, in contrast to their zero thickness counterparts, display manufacturing imperfections resulting from the formwork, casting, and curing processes. Consequently, an ideal assembly that minimizes defects requires a comprehensive understanding of the geometry of each produced module, such as through the utilization of laser scans. The geometric understanding of each module enables a tailored assembly, allowing optimization algorithms to identify the optimal pairing of slits from neighboring modules, taking into account the imperfections of thickness, crease lines, and facet normals of the assembled modules. This ensures that the selected arrangement of modules for assembly is designed to allow imperfections to cancel each other in the assembled state rather than accumulate. An example of a CRC assembly of waterbomb modules is depicted in Fig. 3, where only the self-weight of the modules and a peripheral constraint guarantees a TIA.

Fig. 3: Assembly of carbon reinforced concrete elements where the frame is realized with two steel beams connected by two steel cables (black).

Furthermore, the assembly of two non-zero thickness modules introduces a gap between the facets of the modules, resulting in a non-perfect fit. The gap originates from the assumption that the thickness is uniform throughout the modules, resulting from an offset t perpendicular to the facets, see Fig. 4. Conversely, if the thickness results from an extrusion in the z -direction, a gap will not be formed. Extrusion of the zero thickness module will result in diagonal facets with smaller thickness $t_{\text{facet}} = t \cos \theta$, where t is the thickness of the extrusion and θ is the angle of the facet in relation to the plane.

A module with varying thickness would require a second formwork to enforce this geometrical characteristic, which would add a considerable level of difficulty to the manufacturing process. Therefore, a module with uniform thickness is optimal for the fold-in-fresh approach, as it requires only one formwork given the desired shape of the waterbomb module, and the constant thickness is formed by self-compacting concrete. This comes at the cost that the formed gap must be bridged to ensure proper stress transfer between modules, guaranteeing that the system satisfies its construction purpose. To achieve this, the gap can be filled with a concrete mortar connecting the modules, while steel, ceramic, or rubber patches can be affixed to the facets to ensure contact between all aspects.

Fig. 4: Gap formed by the assembly of non-zero thickness waterbomb modules

Regardless of the method used to address the gaps, establishing contact between the contact facets is crucial to ensure adequate stress transfer between the assembled waterbomb modules. Consequently, parallelism of the normals of the contact facets is a critical geometrical condition that must be ensured. When the facets' normals are misaligned, the self-weight and variable loads will enforce contact between the facets of the waterbomb modules until the system reaches equilibrium, resulting in additional compressive and tensile stresses at the module's cross-section due to bending.

4 Waterbomb interlocking

When the assembly was constructed out of CRC modules, the resulting structure showed load-bearing capabilities, suggesting that the assembly was topologically interlocking. However, to ensure the interlocking property of the proposed assemblies, a mathematical proof is required. In this section, we provide a proof that a family of assemblies made from the proposed module is a TIA by employing various subsets as frames.

4.1 Abstraction of the assembly

In this subsection, we consider an assembly of the waterbomb module as described in Section 2. The investigation is independent of the inclusion of half-modules. We investigate "rectangular" assemblies like the one depicted in Fig. 3. Intuitively we want to talk about *rows* of such assemblies. Specifically, the number of modules in consecutive rows differs by 1. The considered assemblies can be abstracted as a graph containing a vertex for each module and connecting two vertices by an edge, if the corresponding modules are in contact with one another. This abstraction is shown in Fig. 5.

Since each row consists of either $n \in \mathbb{N}$ or $n - 1$ modules we can identify assemblies with a tuple (n, m, f) , where $m \in \mathbb{N}$ is the number of rows, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is the maximum number of modules per row and $f \in \{<, >\}$ a flag, which indicates whether row 1 consists of n or $n - 1$ modules. We denote such an assembly as $\mathcal{A}_{m,n,f}$. Note that m, n and f are not uniquely determined by the assembly as the choice of row 1 is ambiguous. Nevertheless, every choice of m, n and f uniquely defines an assembly $\mathcal{A}_{m,n,f}$.

of copies of the waterbomb module. This is sufficient for our purpose of proving the interlocking property for the proposed assemblies with a suitable frame in the following subsection.

Fig. 5: An assembly abstracted to a graph. The vertices correspond to the waterbomb modules and edges correspond to contact between modules.

4.2 Proof of interlocking property: Rows as frame

In this subsection, we show that an assembly $\mathcal{A}_{m,n,f}$ with its first and m -th row as a frame is a TIA. We can prove that by investigating the contact between two modules. Since modules are connected via linear slits, the only allowed motions of one module relative to another (with which it is in contact) are those that result from translations along the slit and clockwise or counter-clockwise rotations around the slit, depending on the specific connection, see Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Schematic overview of the relative motion between modules. Relative to the center module, the modules have unrestricted translational and rotational motion along the slits. Depending on the slit through which they are connected, the rotation is either clockwise or counter-clockwise.

Therefore, if a module is in contact with two fixed modules through two non-parallel slits, all degrees of freedom of that module are fixed.

Now, consider an assembly $\mathcal{A}_{m,n,f}$ of the proposed waterbomb module. We claim that if the slits of the modules are non-parallel and the modules in the rows with indices 1 and m are selected as a frame, the assembly will be a topological interlocking. The proof is by induction on $m \in \mathbb{N}$ with arbitrary $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

If f has the value " $>$ ", the first row consists of n modules and the second row consists of $n - 1$ modules. Each module in the second row is in contact with two frame modules, and thus, as explained

above, both translation and rotation are restricted. Therefore, we can add the modules in the second row to the frame. We see that the subassembly consisting of the rows 2 to m now also has its outer rows as a frame (see Fig. 7) and thus is a TIA via the induction hypothesis. Since the second row of the assembly is fixed by the frame, all subsets of blocks of the assembly are fixed, because the subassembly is a TIA. Therefore the assembly with m rows is a TIA.

Fig. 7: $\mathcal{A}_{m,n,>}$ with its bottom row (depicted in red) and top row as a frame has an $\mathcal{A}_{m-1,n,<}$ as a subassembly (depicted in black). Since every module in the bottom row of the subassembly is in contact with two frame modules, they are fixed.

If f has the value " $<$ ", the assembly has an $\mathcal{A}_{m,n-1,>}$ as a subassembly with the extremal rows as frame. This subassembly is a TIA by the first case. Since all modules in $\mathcal{A}_{m,n,f}$ not in this fixed subassembly are in contact with two modules of the subassembly (see Fig. 8), the entire assembly is a TIA. This concludes the proof.

Fig. 8: An $\mathcal{A}_{m,n,<}$ with its bottom row (depicted in red) and top row as a frame has an $\mathcal{A}_{m-1,n-1,>}$ as a subassembly (depicted in black). This subassembly is a TIA by the " $>$ "-case. The remaining modules depicted by gray vertices are fixed, because they are in contact with two fixed modules.

4.3 Proof of interlocking property: Corners as frame

It even suffices to fix only the corners of an assembly $\mathcal{A}_{m,n,f}$ of modules with non-parallel slits as the frame (see Fig. 9) to ensure that it is a TIA. This facilitates in practice the construction of an interlocking assembly of the proposed modules using only two cables attached to the frame vertices along the diagonals.

Fig. 9: An assembly where only the corner modules form the frame (depicted in red). This is sufficient for the assembly to be topologically interlocking.

For this, consider a subassembly consisting of the first row and a subset of the second row forming a path with its ends as a frame (see Fig. 10).

Fig. 10: A path of modules with its end as a frame.

Rotational motion between the modules is disallowed, because as depicted in Fig. 6 rotation between blocks would lead to the whole assembly curling up, which contradicts the boundary condition subjected by the frame. Translational motion is also prohibited, as the relative translational motions between two connected modules along the path have a translational motion along the vector connecting the frame modules as a constituent. Thus, every module along the path is fixed. Particularly, all modules forming the first row are fixed and the analogous argument shows, that all modules of row m are fixed. Therefore, the assembly is interlocking by the proof above and the assembly exhibits the topological interlocking property by fixing only the four corner modules.

It has to be noted that this proof of interlocking is purely theoretical and assumes perfect modules with no thickness and infinite stiffness. When trying to build topological interlocking assemblies out of real-world modules, one has to consider imperfections in the material, load transfer between the modules and redundancy, when choosing a suitable frame, as described in the previous section.

5 Conclusion

The exploration of origami-inspired design principles, particularly those derived from the waterbomb tessellation, offers a promising approach to modular structural systems. By introducing slits near the creases of the waterbomb base cells, we can design structural elements suitable for TIAs. The definition and placement of these slits enables the mathematical verification of the interlocking properties of the assemblies. Further research will explore the practical application of these principles in the construction of high-efficiency, lightweight, and environmentally friendly structures. The integration of origami-inspired design with CRC waterbomb modules holds significant potential for innovation in architecture and engineering. The disparity between theoretical models and practical assemblies highlights the need for further developments in the assembly process. Further studies have to tackle the challenge of manufacturing origami inspired folded CRC modules to ensure conformity, optimal load-bearing behavior and a smooth assembly process. An upcoming publication will give a mathematically exact description of the waterbomb module with thickness and a parameter study for the slit location and different assembly techniques.

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